

Oxytocin receptor specifically marks ventromedial intercalated cells of the mouse amygdala

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Graphical abstract

Concept: receptor asymmetry of amygdala intercalated cells

Abstract

Intercalated cells (ITC) of the amygdala gate fear expression and extinction, and are anatomically and functionally divided into dorsomedial (dm; fear expression) and ventromedial (vm; fear extinction) populations. The molecular basis of this functional dichotomy remains incompletely defined. Here, we reanalysed a published single-cell RNA-sequencing dataset of the mouse amygdala (Hochgerner et al., 2023) and examined the neuromodulatory receptor repertoire of four *Foxp2*⁺ ITC clusters (GABA-1 to GABA-4). Using an unbiased Gene Ontology-derived receptor list (705 receptors) and FindAllMarkers with default parameters and Benjamini-Hochberg correction, we identified 74 cluster-enriched receptors (FDR < 0.05). The vm cluster (GABA-1) was defined by *Oxtr*, completely cluster-specific (expressed in 43% of vm cells and 0% of other ITC), together with *Htr2c*, *Cnr1*, *Htr3a*, *Oprk1* and *Sstr2*. The dm-candidate cluster (GABA-4) instead expressed a largely non-overlapping set of receptors (*Adora1*, *Drd3*, *Hrh3*, *Oprk1*, *Chrna7* and *Adra1a*). This receptor-level asymmetry, and in particular the vm-specific oxytocin receptor, provides a candidate molecular handle on the functional distinction between vm and dm ITC in fear processing.

Keywords: intercalated cells; amygdala; oxytocin receptor; fear extinction; single-cell RNA-seq; G-protein-coupled receptor

1. Introduction

The intercalated cell masses (ITC) of the amygdala are clusters of GABAergic neurons that exert inhibitory control over the central and basolateral amygdala and thereby regulate the expression and extinction of conditioned fear. Medial paracapsular ITC are partitioned into a dorsomedial (dm) population that promotes fear expression and a ventromedial (vm) population that supports extinction (Hagihara et al., 2021). Both populations are marked by *Foxp2*, yet the molecular features underlying their opposing contributions to fear behaviour remain unresolved.

Neuromodulatory input is a strong candidate for such a substrate, because receptors for oxytocin, dopamine, opioids and serotonin couple to distinct intracellular cascades that bias a neuron toward potentiation or depression. Using a recently published single-cell atlas of the mouse amygdala (Hochgerner et al., 2023), we performed an unbiased survey of receptor expression across the four *Foxp2*⁺ ITC clusters and tested whether their receptor repertoires are asymmetric in a manner consistent with the dm/vm dichotomy.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Dataset and preprocessing

We reanalysed the mouse amygdala single-cell RNA-sequencing dataset of Hochgerner et al. (2023; 27,998 genes, 55,514 cells) with author-provided cluster annotations. Counts had been normalised by the original authors (counts per 20,000); we applied a \log_2 transformation only. Four *Foxp2*⁺ ITC clusters were retained (GABA-1-*Foxp2*_Fmod, GABA-2-*Foxp2*_Adra2a, GABA-3-*Foxp2*_Col6a1, GABA-4-*Foxp2*_Htr1f; 1,592 cells).

2.2. Receptor gene list

To define receptors without manual selection, we extracted all genes annotated to GO:0004930 (GPCR activity) and GO:0022824 (transmitter-gated ion channel activity) from org.Mm.eg.db, and analysed those present in the dataset.

2.3. Identification of cluster-enriched receptors

Receptors were identified with Seurat FindAllMarkers (v4.4.1; Wilcoxon rank-sum test, each cluster vs the rest, restricted to 705 receptors, only.pos = TRUE). Default parameters were used (min.pct = 0.01, logfc.threshold = 0.1). Because Bonferroni correction over all 27,998 genes is overly conservative here, we applied Benjamini-Hochberg correction over the tested receptors (FDR < 0.05). Principal receptors (*Oxtr*, *Cnr1*, *Drd1*, *Adra2a*) remained significant under stricter thresholds, confirming robustness.

3. Results

Analysis workflow: an unbiased receptor survey of amygdala intercalated cells

Fig. 1. Analysis workflow. The mouse amygdala single-cell RNA-seq dataset (Hochgerner et al., 2023) was preprocessed and four Foxp2⁺ ITC clusters extracted; an unbiased Gene Ontology-derived receptor list was tested with FindAllMarkers under default parameters and Benjamini-Hochberg correction, and the cluster-enriched receptors were visualised by heatmap and DotPlot. A 1,454-gene downstream/synapse set was used for the exploratory downstream analysis.

3.1. The receptor repertoire is asymmetric between vm and dm

The overall analysis workflow is summarised in Fig. 1. Of the GO-derived receptors, 803 were annotated and 705 were present in the dataset; the 98 absent receptors were predominantly olfactory (80) and pheromone (7) receptors, not expected to be expressed in the amygdala (Supplementary Table 3). The four Foxp2⁺ ITC clusters comprised 109 (GABA-1), 448 (GABA-2), 965 (GABA-3) and 70 (GABA-4) cells. Hochgerner et al. (2023) explicitly identified GABA-4 (Foxp2-Htr1f) as an activated ITC population after fear conditioning, “compared to the nonactivated ITC population GABA-1 Foxp2-Fmod” (their Fig. 4d); combined with the dm/vm dichotomy of Hagihara et al. (2021), this motivates treating GABA-1 as the vm population and GABA-4 as the dm candidate, with GABA-3 a striatal D1-like and GABA-2 an adrenergic population.

Of 705 receptors tested, 74 were significantly enriched in at least one cluster (FDR < 0.05; 82 cluster-receptor pairs; complete list in Supplementary Table 1). In GABA-1, Oxtr was completely cluster-specific (43% of GABA-1 cells, 0% of other ITC; log₂FC = 8.23, FDR = 8 × 10⁻³⁰), with Htr2c, Cnr1, Htr3a, Oprk1 and Sstr2 also enriched. GABA-4 expressed a largely non-overlapping set: Adora1, Drd3, Hrh3, Oprk1, Chrna7 and Adra1a (Table 1, Fig. 2). Only Adra1a was shared between GABA-1 and GABA-4. GABA-3 was enriched for Drd1, Gpr88 and Gabra2, and GABA-2 for Adra2a, Gpr83 and Chrm2 (Table 1). Default thresholds brought lowly expressed, cluster-restricted receptors into the testable set and separated GABA-3 from GABA-4.

Table 1. Representative cluster-enriched receptors in naive Foxp2⁺ ITC (FindAllMarkers, BH over 705 receptors, FDR < 0.05).

Cluster (region)	Receptor	Log2FC	pct.1	pct.2	FDR
GABA-1 (vm)	<i>Oxtr</i>	8.23	0.43	0.00	8.1e-30
	<i>Cnr1</i>	4.15	0.87	0.07	5.9e-31
	<i>Htr2c</i>	4.23	0.80	0.10	1.5e-23
	<i>Htr3a</i>	4.08	0.43	0.02	8.7e-18
	<i>Oprk1</i>	3.44	0.40	0.03	3.5e-13
	<i>Sstr2</i>	3.63	0.23	0.01	1.7e-09
	GABA-4 (dm cand.)	<i>Adora1</i>	2.17	0.41	0.12
<i>Drd3</i>		4.21	0.06	0.00	4.6e-03
<i>Hrh3</i>		1.08	0.77	0.39	2.2e-03
<i>Chrna7</i>		4.62	0.06	0.00	4.6e-03
<i>Oprk1</i>		2.23	0.24	0.06	4.3e-03
<i>Adra1a</i>		1.67	0.41	0.16	8.2e-03
GABA-3 (D1-like)	<i>Drd1</i>	1.88	0.63	0.21	9.9e-14
	<i>Gpr88</i>	2.28	0.51	0.16	7.9e-11
	<i>Gabra2</i>	1.17	0.89	0.66	3.8e-13
GABA-2	<i>Adra2a</i>	3.63	0.75	0.14	6.6e-31
	<i>Gpr83</i>	2.15	0.51	0.19	2.8e-09
	<i>Chrm2</i>	2.80	0.24	0.05	5.5e-07

Fig. 2. Heatmap of the 74 cluster-enriched receptors (FDR < 0.05) across the four Foxp2⁺ ITC clusters in the naive state. Colour denotes row-scaled relative expression (z-score). The vm cluster (GABA1_vm) is marked by Oxt, Cnr1, Htr2c and other receptors; the dm-candidate cluster (GABA4_dm) by a largely non-overlapping set including Adora1, Drd3 and Hrh3.

Fig. 3. DotPlot of the 74 cluster-enriched receptors together with cell-type controls (Foxp2, Gad1, Gad2). Dot size denotes the percentage of expressing cells and colour the average expression. The complete vm-restriction of Oxtr and Cnr1 (GABA-1) and the dm-candidate-restricted Adora1, Drd3 and Chrna7 (GABA-4) are directly visible.

The heatmap (Fig. 2) shows this asymmetry directly: on row-scaled relative expression, the vm cluster (GABA1_vm) and dm-candidate cluster (GABA4_dm) form distinct blocks of enriched receptors. In the DotPlot (Fig. 3), the percentage of expressing cells makes the restriction explicit — Oxtr and Cnr1 are present in almost all vm (GABA-1) cells and essentially absent elsewhere, while Adora1, Drd3 and Chrna7 are confined to the dm candidate (GABA-4). On an absolute (non-row-scaled) scale the specificity of receptors that are low in absolute terms, such as Oxtr, is harder to appreciate (Supplementary Fig. 1), confirming that the analysis captures relative cluster enrichment rather than absolute abundance. The expression profile of all 705 receptors, including non-significant ones, is provided in Supplementary Table 2.

3.2. Exploratory analysis of downstream signalling genes

To ask whether the receptor asymmetry extends to downstream effectors, we defined a gene set of 1,454 genes comprising signalling genes downstream of the 74 enriched receptors (452 genes, from neuronal second-messenger Gene Ontology terms) and functional synapse genes (1,130 genes), and tested these genes in two ways.

First, cluster-distinguishing expression at the 2 h timepoint (FindAllMarkers over the gene set, FDR < 0.05) recovered 359 genes, each cluster retaining a distinct repertoire. GABA-1 was marked by *Ngf*, *Oxtr*, *Htr2c* and *Abcc8*; GABA-2 by *Mc4r*, *Ntsr2*, *Adra2a*, *Chrm2*, *Htr1a* and *Ramp2*; GABA-3 by *Drd1*, *Penk*, *Neto1*, *Calb1*, *Tac1* and *Slit2*; and GABA-4 by the synaptic organisers *Cbln1* and *Cbln2*, the NMDA-receptor subunit *Grin2c*, and *Chrm3*, *P2ry1*, *Vip* and *Pvalb* (Supplementary Table 4). Thus the cluster-specific molecular identity seen for receptors is mirrored at the level of downstream and synaptic genes and is maintained at 2 h after fear conditioning.

Second, we compared each cluster between naive and 2 h (FindMarkers, BH correction). The acute response was detectable almost only in GABA-3 (185 naive / 156 cells at 2 h), where 34 genes changed significantly (FDR < 0.05): downregulation of *Camk2a*, *Cacna1e*, *Grm5*, *Ppp3ca* and the immediate-early gene *Egr1* ($\log_2FC = -1.07$), and upregulation of *Gnai1*, *Snap29* and *Rap1a* (Supplementary Table 5). In the vm and dm-candidate clusters the test was underpowered — GABA-1 yielded one significant gene (*Gnb1*) and GABA-4 none (17 naive / 8 cells at 2 h) — so no acute change could be resolved in either population.

4. Discussion

The two ITC populations implicated in opposing aspects of fear behaviour express markedly different neuromodulatory receptors. The vm (extinction-associated) population is uniquely defined by the oxytocin receptor, whereas the dm-candidate (fear-associated) population expresses a largely non-overlapping set of receptors centred on adenosine, dopamine D3, histamine H3 and opioid receptors. The two populations are therefore distinguished not only anatomically and functionally but also by the neuromodulators they are positioned to sense, providing a concrete, receptor-level entry point into the long-standing question of why the dm and vm ITC contribute oppositely to fear and its extinction.

The complete vm-specificity of *Oxtr* is notable. Oxytocin signalling in the central amygdala attenuates conditioned fear (Viviani et al., 2011; Knobloch et al., 2012), and a vm-restricted oxytocin receptor offers a circuit-level mechanism by which oxytocin could selectively bias the ITC network toward extinction. The distinct receptor repertoire of the dm candidate is consistent with this population being regulated by a different set of neuromodulatory inputs.

A caveat concerns the cluster assignment itself: Hochgerner et al. (2023) reported that GABA-3 (*Foxp2*-

Col6a2), the most D1-receptor-enriched ITC cluster, strongly coregulates immediate-early genes at later timepoints and at recall, a dynamic distinct from the acquisition-phase activation of GABA-4. The mapping of the anatomical dm population onto transcriptomic clusters may therefore be one-to-many, with D1-like ITC distributed across GABA-3 and GABA-4; resolving this will require spatial and functional data. GABA-3 was the only cluster in which an acute transcriptional response was statistically resolvable; we present its 2 h changes (Supplementary Table 5) as an exploratory observation, since the vm and dm-candidate populations were too small to test.

Several limitations apply. The assignment of GABA-4 to dm rests on transcriptomic and activation criteria and requires spatial confirmation (e.g. *in situ* hybridisation for *Oxtr*, *Drd1*, *Adora1* along the dorsoventral axis). The receptor asymmetry is robust because the naive populations are adequately sampled, but the acute (2 h) transcriptional response to fear conditioning could not be resolved at the level of downstream signalling and synaptic genes: the relevant clusters are small (vm, 36 cells; dm candidate, 8 cells at 2 h), and no downstream gene reached significance in the dm candidate after correction. Statements about dynamic engagement of receptor signalling therefore remain hypotheses, to be tested by receptor manipulation with functional readouts in identified vm and dm ITC.

In summary, an unbiased receptor survey reveals a clear neuromodulatory asymmetry between vm and dm intercalated cells, centred on a completely vm-specific oxytocin receptor, providing an experimentally addressable framework for the functional dichotomy of amygdala ITC in fear and extinction.

References

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Supplementary material

Supplementary Fig. 1. Heatmap of all 73 receptors with maximum mean expression ≥ 1 across the four clusters, on an absolute (non-row-scaled) colour scale (white to blue). This complements Fig. 2 by showing absolute expression levels; receptors such as Otr, which are low in absolute terms but completely cluster-specific, are de-emphasised here and are best appreciated in Fig. 2.

Supplementary Table 1. Complete list of significant cluster-enriched receptors (82 cluster-receptor pairs; 74 unique receptors; FindAllMarkers, BH-corrected over 705 receptors, FDR < 0.05), with log2FC, pct.1, pct.2 and FDR for every cluster. Provided as a supplementary data file (CSV); representative rows appear in Table 1 of the main text.

Supplementary Table 2. Expression profile of all 705 receptors present in the dataset (Supplementary_all_receptors_naive.csv): mean expression (non-log space) and fraction of expressing cells per cluster, including receptors that were not significant. Representative rows are shown below; the complete table is provided as a CSV.

Receptor	GABA-1 (vm)	GABA-2	GABA-3	GABA-4 (dm)	pct vm	pct dm
Oxtr	0.967	0	0	0	0.433	0
Htr2c	9.8	0.556	0.53	0.235	0.8	0.059
Cnr1	4.633	0.162	0.319	0.176	0.867	0.059
Htr3a	1.2	0.192	0.011	0	0.433	0
Oprk1	1.333	0.162	0.032	0.882	0.4	0.235
Sstr2	0.5	0.02	0.054	0	0.233	0
Adora1	0.167	0.263	0.557	1.882	0.1	0.412
Drd3	0	0	0.022	0.235	0	0.059
Hrh3	1.6	3.727	1.184	4.235	0.533	0.765
Chrna7	0.067	0	0	0.176	0.033	0.059
Adra1a	0.267	0.202	0.908	1.941	0.1	0.412
Drd1	0	0.788	3.951	4.588	0	0.706
Gpr88	0.2	0.596	3.989	3.176	0.1	0.471
Gabra2	2.633	4.141	9.119	5.882	0.6	0.647
Adra2a	0.3	5.758	0.47	0.647	0.133	0.176
Gpr83	0.633	3.505	0.762	1.353	0.233	0.353
Chrm2	0.5	0.919	0.081	0	0.233	0

Supplementary Table 3. The 98 GO-derived receptors absent from the dataset (Supplementary_missing_receptors.csv), classified as follows, confirming that the absent receptors are not expected to be expressed in the amygdala.

Category	Count
Olfactory receptor	80
Pheromone receptor	7
Other	11
Total	98

Supplementary Table 4. Cluster-distinguishing downstream and synaptic genes at 2 h after fear conditioning (downstream_2h_clusterDE.csv; FindAllMarkers over the 1,454-gene downstream/synapse set, only.pos, FDR < 0.05; 359 unique genes), with log2FC, pct.1, pct.2 and FDR for each cluster. Provided as a supplementary data file (CSV); representative genes per cluster are listed in Results 3.3.

Supplementary Table 5. Naive-versus-2 h changes within each cluster (downstream_2h_timechange.csv; FindMarkers over the downstream/synapse set, BH-corrected). GABA-3 showed 34 significant genes (FDR < 0.05); GABA-1 one (Gnb1), GABA-2 one (Pafah1b1) and GABA-4 none, reflecting limited power in the small vm and dm-candidate populations. Representative GABA-3 genes (top up- and down-regulated) are shown below; the complete table is provided as a CSV.

Gene	log2FC (2h/naive)	pct.1	pct.2	FDR
Snap29	+1.95	0.122	0.032	0.044
Chmp2b	+0.80	0.558	0.335	0.009
Rap1a	+0.73	0.468	0.276	0.028
Gnai1	+0.64	0.859	0.735	0.001
Park7	+0.64	0.814	0.697	0.009
Hint1	+0.43	0.981	0.951	0.000
Gria2	-0.21	1.000	1.000	0.028
Ppp3ca	-0.24	1.000	1.000	0.009
Camk2a	-0.25	0.885	0.914	0.047
Cacna1e	-0.53	0.756	0.849	0.003
Kcnb1	-0.57	0.487	0.649	0.028
Lgi1	-0.62	0.590	0.708	0.011
Akap6	-0.64	0.571	0.697	0.009
Hdac4	-0.80	0.256	0.400	0.034
Rgs2	-0.89	0.256	0.389	0.047
Gnal	-0.48	0.763	0.773	0.033
Egr1	-1.07	0.391	0.541	0.028